

AN IMPACT OF ANALYTICS AND INFORMATICS IN COMPUTERIZED INVENTORY MANAGEMENT WITH REFERENCE TO BMTC

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ABSTRACT

In Competitive universe many countries are suffering not for gathering data but solving the available data or generating the available data in all fields in 21st centuries. These as a been one of the crucial battles which has been facing by every country to generate appropriate output based on circumstances.

The developing country like, India has been adopted the big data Analytics and Informatics to overcome the crises of proper data analysis.

Nowadays, due to the pessimistic utilization of resources, we fail to achieve or reach terminal point of every profit-making Commercial houses. In that context it is eagerly to maintain available inventories or stocks in appropriate way through proper tools and techniques called as informatics and Analytics.

The research is focused on the role of analytics and Informatics in logistics management of BMTC transportation. The study reveals that due to the analytics and Informatics techniques the sorting and identifying the inventory turnover ratio has become easy. Since the majority of industries is following Analytics and Informatics techniques which uses Inventory Management system (IMS), it helps to know when to order the stock, how to much order and also provide information about the Minimum Stock of order to be maintained by the BMTC. Due to the adoption IMS software by the BMTC it has helped the employees to work effectively and efficiently. The study suggested that the BMTC will use Justin time techniques (JIT) in inventory management it could augment prior position of BMTC.

Keywords: Public transportation, big data analytics, Inventory Management System Software, Analytics and Informatics.

1. INTRODUCTION

The analysis of data using quantitative and qualitative techniques to look for trends and patterns in the data. Informatics is: A collaborative activity that involves people, processes, and technologies to apply trusted data in a useful and understandable way.

Informatics is **the study of computational systems**. According to the ACM Europe Council and Informatics Europe, informatics is synonymous with computer science and computing as a profession, in which the central notion is transformation of information.

Transportation in India is a largest and varied sector of the economy. Modes of conveyance for transport of goods in India range from people heads and rickshaws to trucks and railroad cars. The national railroad was the major freight hauler independence, but road transport in India grew rapidly after 1947 both rail and road transport important.

The share of India transportation investment in total public investment declined during the period from the early 1950s to the early 1980s, real public transportation investment also declined during much of that period because of the need for funds in the rest of the economy. As a consequence, by the early 1980s the system in India was barely meeting the needs the nation or preparing for future economic growth.

Many roads, for example, were breaking up because of overuse and lack of maintenance, rail roads required new track and rolling stock. Ports needed equipment and facilities, particularly for bulk and container cargo, and at many airports national civil airlines needed supporting equipment, including provision for instruments landings. The government planned to devote 19% of the eight five plan (1992-1996) budget to transportation and communication, up from the 16% devoted to the sector during the 7th plan.

Although there is a largest private sector involvement in transportation in India, the government plays a large regulatory and development role. The central government has ministries to handle civil aviation, railroads and surface counterpart agencies are found at the state and union territory level, improving the entire transportation sector in the late 1990s in the ability of the sector to adjust to the central government's national reform initiatives, including privatization, deregulation and reduced subsidies. The sector must also adjust to foreign tread expansions, demographic pressures increasing urbanization, technological change and public safety concerns.

India has a major railroad, equipment production industry. Although some state-of-the-art electrical capacity to meet most of it standards locomotive and passengers, cars and ancillary equipment needs and has made plans to export locomotives. The research, design, and standards organization of Indian railways engages in research and simulation aimed include high speed passengers train (upto 140 km per hours) and freight train (up to 80 km per hours) and solid signaling equipment. Because some 2/3 of the Nations freight carried by train, there is a serious freight car shortage. To overcome this and other industry related transportation problems, Indian railway envision having to import up to 5000 freight cars a year

2. INVENTORY MANAGEMENT

Inventory management is the process of efficiently overseeing the constant flow of units into and out of an existing stock of goods. This process usually involves controlling the transfer of units in order to prevent the inventory from becoming too high, or dwindling to levels that could put the operation of the company into jeopardy. Inventory management is primarily about specifying the size and placement of stocked goods. Inventory management is required at different locations within a facility or within multiple locations of a supply network to protect the regular and planned course of production against the random disturbance of running out of materials or goods. The scope of inventory management also concerns the fine lines between replenishment lead time, carrying costs of inventory, asset management, inventory forecasting, inventory valuation, inventory visibility, future inventory price forecasting, physical inventory, available physical space for inventory, quality management, replenishment, returns and defective goods and demand forecasting. Planning and controlling of inventory management is concerned with the following three basic questions:

3. COMPUTERIZED INVENTORY MANAGEMENT

A Computerized inventory management system enables a company to monitor inventory levels in real time throughout the day. Also known as Inventory management software, businesses can stay updated with inventory orders, counts and sale. A computerized inventory management system can help you avoid costly mistakes, get your whole team on the same page, and help you keep track of inventory from anywhere. By using a computerized

inventory system, all aspects of your business will run like a well-oiled machine. Sort is the simplest, easiest way to track your inventory plus, with our bulk import feature, it takes minutes to get a spreadsheet worth of data imported in to sort.

4. FEATURES OF COMPUTERIZE INVENTORY MANAGEMENT

a) Real-time inventory tracking

- Real-time inventory value
- Proper inventory reporting
- Reorder levels and low stocks alerts
- Purchase management and supplier management.

b) Objectives

- To explore the function of informatics and analytics in BMTC Inventory Management.
- To know the progress of inventory management in BMTC via AI.

c) Difficulties in the Manual Inventory System

The current system operates manual inventory system, from stocks, products, ordering and purchases etc... recorded in a book. This is faced with errors, incompleteness, and insufficient data for analysis. Information regarding stocks, products, sales and purchases are still in black and white which is not properly organized and managed. From the wholesalers to retailer bills, tickets, vouchers, receipts of products are recorded in a book but further operations are not being properly handled. As a result, it is difficult in processing, updating and managing. The factors for these difficulties are:

1. Time Consumption
2. Poor Communication
3. Physical Counts
4. Daily Purchases
5. Ordering Supplies

d) Types of inventory management system

- Manual inventory management
- Periodic inventory system
- Barcode inventory system
- Radio frequency identification
- Perpetual inventory system

5. SERVICES OFFERED BY BMTC

As on JULY 16, 2019, there are a total of 6639 buses and electric buses 90 in 2022 running in BMTC.

Ordinary bus services which are used for transportation can be classified as:

- Blue and White: the old ordinary buses with ordinary fares. Buses introduced after 2001 have pneumatic doors.

- White and Blue: The Parisara Vahini ordinary buses introduced between 2002 and 2008 with pneumatic doors.
- Blue buses: The ordinary buses under the JNNURM scheme with low floors and LED boards.

The following are the special service apart from ordinary service run by BMTC:

- SUVARNA
- PUSHPAK
- BIG 10
- BIG CIRCLE
- TRAL SARIGE
- VAJRA
- VAYU VAJRA
- MARCO POLO AC and CORONA AC
- METRO FEEDER

6. MAJOR ELECTRIC BUS STATIONS IN BANGALURU

- DEPOT 37: kengari deport, where 1st Electric bus were started
- DEPOT 8: Yeshwanthpur, 2nd
- DEPOT 29: K.R.PURAM, 3rd

7. SMART CARD

BMTC offered 10 cycles from from Shanthinagar and shivajinagar bus stations on February 15, 2017. The smart card can be used to purchase bus tickets and can be activated up to 10,000 (\$150). Provide tangible evidence of fulfilling over 10000 customer expectations. As noted by HUBBank, BMTC's partner in the project, the smart card is "India's first contactless open circuit EMV card". The cards "open circuit" architecture allows different organizations to integrate their own smart card schemes by adopting BMTC smart card instructions.

8. FARES

BMTC salaries are considered to be among the best in the country for entry-level position. In any case it will not be expensive in later stages. They range from Rs.4 per km in the main stages to Rs.1/- per km as the separation increases. BMTC features is Rs.70 (Rs.65/- for BMTC personal cards holders) daily card. It can be used for movement in any bus except air and refrigerated buses. This is a midnight project and accessible to all conductors when purchases come in. Air conditioning bus lane can be accessed for Rs 100. When creating identity card (voter card, driver's permit, etc.) BMTC will give 25% lane concession to senior citizens in a wide range of buses from September 1, 2008.

9. TUMMOC

Tummoc was the answer to the hassle of regular transportation options and the struggle to find reasonable price short term rides in Bengaluru. The absurdity of a 20-minute wait for a 10 minute ride in the metro or a bus, and the difficulty fulfilling the first and last mile requirements when using public transport, formed the base of the tummoc experience.

The core of our motivation to create tummoc as an offering was that while India has an extensive network of public transport, which are priced affordably as well, we still don't see public transport as a legitimate commute option. It's only ever chosen out of desperation, and never by choice.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Literature review is the most important and the second step in the process of any research. First of all, let us understand what does literature review exactly means in research, a literature review is a comprehensive summary of previous research on a topic. To be more specific a literature review is a search and evaluation of the available existing literature in the given subject or a chosen topic area. It provides an overview of current knowledge, allowing you to identify relevant theories, methods and gaps in the existing research. A good literature review doesn't just summarize source it analyses, synthesizes and critically evaluates to give a clear picture of the state of knowledge on the subject.

The literature is reviewed on the similar subject and few relevant research findings are summarized for presenting an overview of relationship of dependent and independent variables and understanding outcomes/concluding remarks given by the researchers in their research work. It shows what had already done and what type of work yet to be carried out. It shows the direction in which the research direction must go. Research work clearly shows there should not be any duplication of work.

A various types of research studies have been conducted on various aspects of computerized inventory management for several industries, which is relevant for this research. Some worthwhile studies relating to the present study viewed here.

(tim, 2022) Has studied that computerized inventory system allows a corporation to keep track of inventory levels throughout the day in real time. Businesses may keep track of inventory orders, counts, and sales with inventory management software. A computerized inventory system can help you prevent costly mistakes, understand what is and isn't moving. Then bring your entire staff on board, and keep track of inventory from anywhere. All areas of your organization will work like a well-oiled machine if you use a computerized inventory system. (tim, 2022)

(KHENG, 2015) Has concentrated on the computerized inventory management (IMS) which has been introduced to increase the efficiency despite having a large storage and making possible to search the information or a specific item in a short time. Even real time item monitoring is possible for the user can make modify or view the storage status and item status with a few clicks by their fingertips. Computerized Inventory Management System involved a computer loaded with a software capable of interacting with user using Graphical User Interface and capable of registering new items, deleting items, modifying items details, generate a label for each item.

(ZASSHI, 2005) Has guided that computerized (Automation) in the drug distribution process is helpful to pharmacists in creating new clinical services. We have ameliorated the drug inventory control system seamlessly connected with the physician order-entry system. This control system application, named Artima, allows inventory functions to be faster and more efficient in real time. Artima can search the lot number and expiration date of drug in the purchase and delivery records. The workload in the inventory management in each section of the Pharmacy Department as well as in clinical units was dramatically reduced after the implementation of this system. The automation system in the drug inventory management allows creating new clinical positions for pharmacists. This system also could pay for itself in time.

(Saenz, 1975) Has researched on the topic computerized inventory management which deals with that of maintaining the inventory at certain levels, in order to reduce costs and obtain a better company operation. And also helps in providing real time inventory management in the company. Where it covers economic order quantity, economic order point, safety stock, ABC analysis classification of item

(Walsh, 1974) The authors' first purpose in his research effort was to determine the extent to which small businesses are utilizing the computerized inventory management method and services. The study was focused upon the specific area of inventory management control in manufacturing businesses. The author has provided a statistical picture of the degree and nature of use of computerized inventory control among the specified type of businesses. The author has also determined whether a significant correlation existed between specific features of inventory of categories of items, monetary value and seasonal fluctuations.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

One of the basic and important objectives of any business organization is to make profit and exist in the market for longer period of time. This profit can be achieved through selling goods or rendering services. The profit earned by an organization depends on the cost of factors of production and the prevailing competition. The base for fixing the selling price is the cost of manufacturing the profit percentage varies depending on the cost of manufacturing the manufacturing company ascertains the cost on the unit manufactured. But the problem is faced by the organization institution rendering services. It depends on the skill of an individual or concerned type of service say for example; hotel business, hospital, electrical, transport etc.

Need for the Study:

Inventory management facilitates the smooth functioning of business and enhances sales, promotes cost-effectiveness, and improves customer experience in every Industry.

BMTC is one of the oldest and biggest transport industry in Karnataka which offered ample of services to the public. So, it needs an hour to understand how the inventory management is practiced in BMTC through AI.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY:

- To study the method of inventory management by applying analysis and informatics techniques by BMTC.
- To study the flow and application of inventory management system (IMS) in the BMTC.
- To study about the inventory management system (IMS) software adopted by stores and purchase department of BMTC for managing the inventory in daily basis.

SCOPE OF THE STUDY

A particular emphasis of the research will be conducted at Shantinagar BMTC workshop Bangalore, Karnataka, India's BMTC (Bangalore Metropolitan Transport Corporation). The major backdrop of the inquiry will be BMTC's inventory management system, which includes a variety of inventory items such office supplies, fuel, maintenance materials, and bus parts.

LIMITATION OF THE STUDY

- The study is restricted to only BMTC Workshop at Shantinagar.
- The Study is analyzed for 5 years.

➤ The Study is confirmed to Inventory Management of BMTC.

METHODOLOGY

The research study's methodology section describes the strategy and techniques that were employed. In order to give a thorough examination of how analytics and informatics systems have impacted BMTC's inventory management process, quantitative data was included in this study, which looks into the impact of these technologies on computerized inventory management at the BMTC. The secondary data has been extracted from journal, website, articles and Reports of BMTC.

Primary Data Collection: Surveys on inventory management were conducted at the BMTC workshop in Shantinagar. Gathered data on inventories during the previous five years, which are kept up to date at the workshop using an Inventory Management software system. Data was gathered about the following topics: increased productivity, reduced costs, accurate inventory monitoring, simplicity of use and training requirements, and satisfaction with the analytics and informatics tools following the implementation of IMS Software in the BMTC workshop for inventory management.

Secondary Data Collection:

Company records: Examination of BMTC's internal records over the last few years concerning costs, stock-outs, surplus inventory, and inventory turnover rates.

Academic and Industry Literature: Case studies and academic articles about informatics and analytics in inventory management systems are reviewed.

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

1. The following table shows the LIQUID UREA CONSUMPTION (in liters) from 2019-20 to 2023-24 (up to 31-08-2024) by BMTC.

Years	2019-20	2020-21	2021-22	2022-23	2023-24
Total Liters	434268	716250	643725	262500	377845

Source: Survey Data

Analysis:

Table number 1, it can be analyzed that there is a cyclical fluctuation in the liquid urea consumption held by BMTC during the last five years i.e. from 2019-20 to 2023-24 (up to 31-08-2024) by 434268, 716250, 643725, 262500 and 377845 respectively.

Graph: -

Interpretation:

From the above table and graph, it can be inferred that there is a cyclical fluctuation in the liquid urea consumption held by BMTC, over the period of last five years i.e., from 2019-20 to 2023-24(up to 31-08-2024).

In 2019-20 it was (434268) total liters, in 2020-21 it was (716250) there was increase in the liquid urea consumption, in 2021-22 it was (643725) total liters, in 2022-23 it was (262500) total liters’ consumption, means there was decrease in the consumption of liquid urea from 2019 to 2021. And in 2023-24 (up to up to 31-08-2024) it was (377845).

Due to Covid-19 impact the liquid urea consumption from 2020-21 to 2021-22 was gradual declined in the BMTC.

2. The following table shows the ENGINE OIL CONSUMPTION (in liters) by BMTC.

Years	2019-20	2020-21	2021-22	2022-23	2023-24
Grade	TM +				
Total Liters	269850	269850	126000	148715	52890

Source: Survey Data

Analysis:

Table Number 2, it can be analyzed that there is a cyclical fluctuation in the Engine oil consumption of Grade (TM+) held by BMTC during the last five years i.e. from 2019-20 to 2023-24(up to 31-08-2024) by 269850,269850,126000,148715 and 52890 respectively.

Interpretation:

From the above table and graph it can be inferred that there is a cyclical fluctuation in the Engine oil consumption held by BMTC, over the period of last five years i.e. from 2019-20 to 2023-24(up to 31-08-2024)

In 2019-20 it was (269850) total liters, in 2020-21 it was stagnant consumption of previous year of (269850) liters, in 2021-22 there was decrease of consumption to (126000) total liters, in 2022-23 there was increase of consumption to (148715) total liters. And in 2023-24 (up to 31-08-2024) it was (52890) Engine Oil Consumption.

Due to COVID -19 and Introduction of BMTC Electric Vehicle in the period of 2020-21 to 2021-22 so there is a less consumption of Engine oil by BMTC buses. Hence there is a decrease in the period of 2021-22.

3. The following table shows the WHEEL BEARING GREASE CONSUMPTION (IN KILO GRAM) of W/B grease grade held by BMTC.

Year	2019-20	2020-21	2021-22	2022-23	2023-24
Total	31122	34186	35040	16562	39485
Liters					

Source: Survey Data

Analysis: -

Table Number 3, it can be analyzed that there is increase of wheel bearing grease consumption by BMTC during 2019-20, 2020-21, 2021-22 by 31122, 34186, 35040. There was a decrease in the year 2022-23 by 16562 and again began to increase in the year 2023-24 by 39485 respectively.

Graph

Interpretation

From the above table and graph it can have inferred that there is increase of consumption of wheel bearing grease till the year of 2021-22. In the year 2019-20 the wheel bearing grease consumption was 31122. In the year 2020-21 the wheel bearing grease consumption was 34186. In the year 2021-22 the wheel bearing grease consumption was 35040. Thereafter the consumption was reduced to 16562 by the different depots in the year 2022-23. In the year 2023-24 the wheel bearing grease consumption was 39485 by the different depots.

This is because the running of BMTC buses during the year 2022-23 was decreased due to impact of COVID -19 many people started dining of usage of public transport and started using the personal vehicles.

4. The following table shows the POWER STEERING OIL CONSUMPTION (IN LITERS) P/S Oil of grade held by BMTC.

YEAR	2019-20	2020-21	2021-22	2022-23	2023-24
TOTAL LITERS	26150	16955	17068	7573	10010

Source: Survey Data

Analysis: -

Table Number 4, it can be analysed that there is increase and decrease of power steering oil consumption held by BMTC during the last five years i.e. from 2019-20 to 2023-24 by 26150, 16955, 17068, 7573 and 10010 respectively.

Graph

Interpretation

From the above graph can inferred that there is increase of power starring oil consumption in the year 2019-20 by 26150 total LTRS. And in the year 2020-21 power starring oil consumption was reduced to 16955 total LTRS. And in the year 2021-22 power starring oil consumption was increased to 17068 total LTRS. And in the year 2022-2023 power starring oil consumption was reduced to 7573. And in the year 2023-24 power starring oil consumption was increased to 10010 total liters.

There is a cyclical fluctuation in the power oil consumption by the depots of BMTC year by year. Due to impact of covid-19 there was decline in the consumption after 2020-21.

5. The following table shows **the Coolant Consumption (in LTRS) 50/50** ration held by BMTC.

Year	2019-20	2020-21	2021-22	2022-23	2023-24
Total Liters	236460	203700	185855	110250	116970

Source: Survey Data

Analysis

From the above table it can be analysed that there is a decrease of coolant consumption held by BMTC during the last five years i.e. from 2019-20 to 2023-24 by 236460,203700,185855,110250 and 116970 respectively.

Graph: -

Interpretation

From the above Table and graph it can be inferred that there is a gradual decrease in the coolant consumption held by BMTC, over a period of last five years. In the year 2019-20 the coolant consumption was 236460, and in the year 2020-21 the coolant consumption was 203700 and in the year 2021-22 the coolant consumption was 185855 total LTRS, in the year 2022-23 the coolant consumption was 110250 total liters, and in the year 2023-24 the coolant consumption was 116970 total liters.

The coolant consumption was decreased every year which was held in BMTC. Due to lack of usage of buses during the covid-19 period.

FINDINGS

- ❖ There was a cyclical fluctuation of liquid urea consumption held by BMTC from 2019-20 to 2023-24(up to 31-08-2024) by 434268 to 377845.
- ❖ There was a cyclical fluctuation in the Engine oil consumption held by BMTC from 2019-20 to 2023-24(up to 31-08-2024) by 269850 to 269850.
- ❖ There is increase of wheel bearing grease consumption by BMTC from 2019-20 to 2023-24(up to 31-08-2024) by 31122 to 35040.
- ❖ There is an increase and decrease of power steering oil consumption held by BMTC from 2019-20 to 2023-24(up to 31-08-2024) by 26150 to 10010.
- ❖ There is a decrease of coolant consumption held by BMTC from 2019-20 to 2023-24(up to 31-08-2024) by 236460 to 116970.

SUGGESTIONS

- The BMTC has to adopt the Just in Time (JIT) Technique in order to reduce the order of cost and to work effectively and efficiently.
- BMTC should adopt the better AI Techniques for up gradation, modernization.
- The BMTC should insist the employees about the AI Technique importance and significance.

CONCLUSION

I conclude that BMTC has adopted **IMS** software for managing the inventory which is an one of the AI Tool, the IMS software was developed by interlace India. The inventory management system provide data regarding the purchase of inventory from different company in the tender process and also provide information about the total number of inventories consumed by the different depots of BMTC. The IMS software also provides information of receipts and payment regarding the inventory and also the about the scrape revenue of BMTC generated by inventory. Online reservation has pleased the transportation problem of commuters.

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